

COVID-19 AND UNPRIVILEGE CLASS: AN ANALYSIS

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The World Health Organization's (WHO) guidelines for safety against COVID-19 are extremely simple & basic. The guidelines states people to wash their hands regularly with soap, practice social distancing, with a strict stay at home if one happens to be in an affected area or has been exposed to the virus in any way possible. Home quarantine is also advised for people who are in or have recently visited (in the past 14 days) COVID-19 affected areas to avoid the spread of the disease (World Health Organization, nd). India's most populated state with over 200 million people, Uttar Pradesh has managed well to keep the cases below 500 (451 at the time of writing). The state has further sealed all the 160 hotspots completely. Uttar Pradesh had no laboratory to test the Sars-CoV-2 pathogen when the first positive case was reported on 3 March; it now has 10. The state government has established a Covid Care Fund, and is getting support from public representatives and the general public. The money is being used to expand testing and treatment facilities; 2,400 tests are being done daily. The government is already working to boost the manufacturing units of PPE, N95 masks, triple-layer masks, thermal analysers, ventilators and other equipment.

Since healthcare systems in progressive nations, like the United States (US), United Kingdom (UK), & Italy, has failed to contain the rapid increase in the number of cases, then in this case it becomes crucial to follow such advice to pre-empt the spread of this dangerous virus, especially in low- & middle-income countries where healthcare systems are a luxury for millions to afford. The reality of such a densely populated country like India, it becomes questionable as how practical it is to adhere to these guidelines? It is the question every mind follows and is scared to even admit to self. By examining and analyzing the latest National Sample Survey Office (NSSO) reported data on housing & sanitation (76th round, 2018), we make an assessment of the accessibility & availability of basic housing & related amenities of an average Indian household, such as sanitation facilities, which are set at minimum requirements in order to follow WHO guidelines effectively. We consider per capita availability of rooms, access to fresh hygienic water for bathing & toilet facilities as fundamentals to comply with the social distancing norms and to maintain hygiene.

Cheek-by-jowl Living Spaces

Investigating on the housing substructure in India, it reveals that almost a third of the rural population & a half of the urban population in India live in houses which as per capita space available are less than a single room, which effectively means that isolating

a person with risk of infection is extremely difficult in these compact spaces. This implies that home quarantine/self-isolation measures would be difficult to implement among 60% of the population of India in the event of spread of infection (Table 1).

Table 1: Per Capita Availability of Rooms

	Rural	Urban	Total
Less than a room	66.08	45.16	59.6
Just a room	14.71	17.1	15.45
More than one room	19.21	37.74	24.95
Total	100	100	100

Water Woes

Accessibility of running water in homes is an important part of hygiene and a necessity to ensure regular hand washing with soap. The NSSO data reveals that 40% of urban households & 75% of rural households in India do not have access to tap water in their homes or even in radius of their residential premises (Table 2).

Table 2: Source of Water

Drinking Water Domestic Needs

Source	Rural	Urban	Total	Rural	Urban	Total
Bottled water	3.4	10.3	5.5	0.1	0.4	0.2
Piped water into houses	11.5	43.7	21.4	13.9	49.6	24.8
Piped water to yard/plot	9.8	14.1	11.1	9.8	10.8	10.1
Piped water from neighbor	0.8	1.0	0.8	0.8	0.9	0.8

Source	Rural	Urban	Total	Rural	Urban	Total
Public tap/standpipe	9.1	7.1	8.5	7.4	5.4	6.8
Tube well	10.8	10.3	10.7	11.5	17.2	13.2
Hand pump	45.3	8.0	33.9	41.4	7.9	31.2
Well: Protected	2.9	1.6	2.5	2.7	2.4	2.6
Well: Unprotected	4.3	2.5	3.7	4.5	2.8	4.0
Tanker truck: Public	0.1	0.8	0.3	0.1	0.5	0.5
Tanker truck: Private	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.5
Spring: Protected	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.2
Spring: Unprotected	0.3	0.0	0.2	0.4	0.0	0.3
Rainwater Collection	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.1
Surface water: Tank/Pond	0.4	0.1	0.3	4.9	1.0	3.7
Other surface water (river, dam, stream, canal, lake, etc.)	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.2
Others (cart with small tank or drum, etc.)	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.2
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100

It implies that majorly households obtain their basic resource of water from public taps, wells, or other shared water sources. This denotes that while maintaining any sort of hygiene & social distancing is itself difficult in these unusual circumstances, there is a higher risk of contamination of water resource & also the spread of infections during public health crises.

Furthermore, it has been observed that average time required to collect water from community sources is close to approximately an hour every day, certainly implying that social distancing is difficult task to follow & execute for a large proportion of households with no proper regulations & measures for this daily need crisis (Table 3b). As is the practice in many developing or under-developed countries, the liability of collecting water from open resources is predominantly on females of the household (73%) exposing them to greater health risks (Table 3c).

Table 3: Access to Drinking Water

	Rural	Urban	Total
(a) Access to drinking water			
Within dwelling	30	59	39
Outside dwelling but within the premises	31	22	28
Outside premises			
Less than 0.2 km	28.6	13.7	24.0
0.2 km to 0.5 km	8.0	3.2	6.5
0.5 km to 1.0 km	2.1	1.2	1.8
1.0 km to 1.5 km	0.4	0.4	0.4
1.5 km or more	0.5	0.5	0.5
Total	100	100	100

	Rural	Urban	Total
(b) Average time (in minutes) required to fetch water in a day from outside premises	48.5	40.0	47.0
(c) Who fetches water?			
Male members	20.8	33.8	23.0
Female members	77.5	56.6	73.9
Hired labour	0.6	4.7	1.3
Others	1.1	4.9	1.8
Total	100	100	100

Poor Sanitation Facilities

Following on, we examine Indians access to exclusive washrooms & latrines required to maintain hygiene to avoid coming into contact with viral discharges of infected persons (Table 4). Among the rural households, 45% have no access to exclusive washrooms, & 39% have no access to exclusive latrines, while 5% each use public facilities.

In urban areas, while the percentage of people without access to washrooms & latrines are lower at 9% & 4% respectively, a higher proportion of households use common/public washrooms & latrines (11% & 13.5% respectively).

Overall, about 8% of the Indian population uses public sanitation facilities & a quarter of the population has no access to any sanitation facility, making it difficult to follow good hygiene.

Table 4: Access to Bathrooms & Latrines

	Bathrooms			Latrines		
	Rural	Urban	Total	Rural	Urban	Total
For the exclusive use of household	51.5	79.7	60.2	65.0	82.2	70.2
For common use of households in a building	4.8	10.7	6.6	5.7	10.6	7.2
Public/community use without payment	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	1.5	0.6
No bathroom	0	0	0	0	1.2	0.4
Others	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.5	0.4	0.4
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100

Prevalence of proper hand-washing practices

Finally, we examine hand-washing practices amongst Indians, prior to meals & after defecation to comprehend in what way these are strongly embedded is this idea of washing or cleaning hands with soap & water (Table 5). We find that while 75% of the population washes their hands using soap & water after defecation whereas only 34% of it performs cleaning of hand before having a meal. The majority of the population (62%) uses only water to wash hands before meals. This displays that the fundamental practice required to curtail infections through hand-washing with soap several times a day is a practice that majority of Indians are yet to adopt.

Table 5: Hand-washing Practices

	Rural	urban	Total
(a) Hand-washing regularly before meals			
With water & soap detergent	25.0	55.3	34.3
With water & ash mud/sand etc.	3.6	1.4	2.9
With water only	70.1	42.7	61.7
Do not wash	1.3	0.6	1.1
Total	100	100	100
(b) Hand-washing regularly after defecation			
With water & soap detergent	68.4	89.2	74.7
With water & ash mud/sand etc.	18.1	2.1	13.2
With water only	13.5	8.7	12.0
Do not wash	0.1	0.0	0.1
Total	100	100	100

Our study & breakdown of the situation exhibits that maintaining social-distancing, following proper hygiene, & observing self-isolation guidelines in the case of this deadly infection are practically difficult for majority of the population residing in India, due to existing housing patterns & sanitation facilities. Even if information regarding protective measures & safety norms is circulated to reach & go rounds through the entire population, the lack of basic amenities & resources makes the financially & resourcefully less-privileged sections of the Indian society defenceless against COVID-19.

<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/>
India shares two SARS-CoV-2 genome sequences